

6G-SANDBOX

Supporting Architectural and technological
Network evolutions through an intelligent, secured
and twinning enabled Open eXperimentation
facility

Deliverable D5.1

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System

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ABSTRACT

This document provides an overview of various aspects related to testing and experimentation within the 6G-SANDBOX project. It outlines the concepts around the experiment lifecycle manager, how test cases and scenarios and other relevant testing and experimentation related aspects. These aspects are mapped to tools and solutions that support the features and functionalities needed to realize the concepts. The supporting tools are centring around OpenTAP and KS8500 test automation cloud platform, which will support internal and external testers and experimenters in creating, managing, and executing tests and experiments. The document also lists the portfolio of tools and equipment made available within the 6G-SANDBOX facility that can be controlled and interacted with through the test automation cloud platform. Additionally, the document also describes how KPIs from test and experiments are extracted, stored, and visualized. Finally, the document describes how evaluation is implemented in the form of tests to validate KPIs of network and infrastructure, and also how project's internal use cases will be evaluated. Overall, the document outlines what tooling and functionalities are available in the 6G-SANDBOX project to support testers and experimenters in evaluating 6G related technologies.

KEYWORDS

KPI, KVI, Monitoring, Trial network, Experiment, Test, Tools, ELCM, TNLCM, Automation, Testing methodology

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE

The core part of the document is divided into the following sections:

- Section 2 “6G-SANDBOX Testing Methodology Summary” offers a description of the 6G-SANDBOX Testing methodology. This methodology was briefly described in D2.1 [1], and is based in previous work from the 5Genesis and Evolved-5G projects.
- Section 3 “6G-SANDBOX Test and Experiment Automation” explains how tests can be defined and executed using the Experiment Life Cycle Manager in the form of a test automation cloud platform made available in 6G-SANDBOX.
- Section 4 “Testing and Measurement Equipment in 6G-SANDBOX Platforms” gives an overview and introduction to all tools and equipment made available within the project, to support diverse and advanced testing and experimentation.
- Section 5 “6G-SANDBOX Testing Reporting” explains how KPIs are produced and collected in the 6G-SANDBOX Monitoring system of the Trial Networks and how Experimenters can get access to these data.
- Section 6 “6G-SANDBOX KPI and KVI Measurement Implementation” gives an overview of the current state of KPI and KVI evaluations both related to infrastructure, trial networks, and 6G SANDBOX project internal use cases.

1.2 TARGET AUDIENCE

The release of the deliverable is public, intending to expose the overall 6G-SANDBOX facility to a wide variety of research individuals and communities. From specific to broader, different target audiences for D2.1 [1] are identified as detailed below:

- The Project Consortium to validate that all objectives and proposed technological advancements have been analysed and to ensure that, through the identified requirements (functional and non-functional), the next actions can be concretely derived. Furthermore, the deliverable sets to establish a common understanding among the Consortium with regards to: i) the Facility architecture to be set for reference, and ii) the technologies to be utilised, deployed and extended per platform.
- The Research Community and funding EC Organization to: i) summarize the 6G-SANDBOX scope, objectives and intended project innovations, ii) detail the 6G-SANDBOX Facility and the four platforms as well as the targeted use cases that shall be demonstrated and measure provided technological advancements, and iii) present the related requirements and associated KPIs that must be addressed to achieve the expected results;
- The vertical actors that will be engaged to the project with the process of the open calls and will utilise the 6G-SANDBOX facility to conduct their experiments.
- The general public for obtaining a better understanding of the framework and scope of the 6G-SANDBOX project.

1.3 TESTING AND EXPERIMENTATION TERMINOLOGY

Throughout the document the concepts of testing and experimentation will be extensively used. Therefore, it is crucial to explicitly define the precise meanings of these terms in this section.

The goal of an **experiment** is to explore the performance or functionality of an entity. A specific target is not formally set upfront, but the goal is to explore limits and capabilities of the target entity.

The goal of a **test** is to validate the performance or functionality of an entity. There are specific goals or thresholds set that the test seeks to reach or prove that performance goes beyond or below. Subsequently, a test can be evaluated as passed or failed depending on the evaluation of outcome in relation to the targets or thresholds.

From this, an experiment can be seen as a more loosely defined methodology than a test.

2 6G SANDBOX TESTING METHODOLOGY SUMMARY

2.1 TESTING METHODOLOGY DESCRIPTION

Though each Experimenter is free to use whichever testing methodology they prefer, or even to compare different methodologies, the 6G-SANDBOX project provides a default Testing and Experimentation methodology, originally defined as a result of the 5Genesis & 5G-VINNI H2020 project.

This methodology is based on the creation of three different textual descriptions, each defining a different part of the process and conditions:

1. Test Cases, which define the main goals and general process for the experiment.
2. Scenarios, which define the radio conditions.
3. Slices, which specify the set of available resources.

Each of these descriptions can then be re-used and mixed, with each combination producing a different Experiment definition. Experimenters may also define Experiment Campaigns, where a single Test Case is executed along a different set of Scenarios and Slices, each generating results that can be used to compare the performance in different radio conditions and/or resource allocation.

2.2 TEST CASES DEFINITION

Test Cases are textual descriptions, following a certain template, that provide details on the intention, expected outcomes, and process required to obtain a certain set of KPIs or KQIs. Test Cases usually include:

- Target KPIs and KQIs to be measured by an implementation of the Test Case, as well as some context related to the KPIs/KQIs, goals, and reasoning behind the Test Case. A Test Case may also include information about additional measurements that can be obtained along with the main expected results.
- Methodology followed by the Test Case, including:
 - Methods for calculating the Test Case outputs (KPIs or KQIs) based on the raw measurements obtained.
 - Considerations about the validity and statistical significance of the results (e.g., number of repetitions of the test sequence, minimum duration of the test, etc.).
- A sequence of steps to follow in order to generate the required results, as well as the expected outcome for each of the steps.
- Expected pre-conditions that must be met before the execution of the test sequence (e.g., the minimum set of features supported by the equipment, pre-configurations, physical conditions, etc.).

In order to allow re-usability of Test Cases in different conditions, the radio configuration and the availability of resources during the experiment are defined separately, as Scenarios and Slices, that are interchangeable. Scenarios and Slices are described in the following sections. In most situations, the Test Cases are not expected to include specific details about how to execute each step in the test sequence, or how to reach the expected pre-conditions, which also allows re-usability in different platforms or with alternative equipment.

For the actual execution of a Test Case, the test logic must be fine-tuned for the capabilities of each particular platform. This implies that different Test Case implementations will exist; however, as long as the guidelines of the Test Cases are followed, the results obtained by different implementations should be replicable and comparable.

2.3 TEST SCENARIOS

Scenarios provide guidelines on how to configure real or emulated radio equipment, in order to simulate different conditions that can affect the performance of a User Equipment. Scenarios can define, for example, conditions that affect radio coverage (direct or no line-of-sight, distance to the antennas, etc.), network congestion, mobility (UEs in static positions, pedestrian or vehicular movements), among others.

As for Test Cases, considering the availability of different radio equipment with different capabilities and configuration interfaces, Scenarios do not provide specific configuration values tailored for certain devices, instead providing guidelines for emulating the desired conditions.

2.4 SLICES FOR TESTING

Slices, as defined in the original Open5Genesis Methodology [2], represent the portion of the computational, networking, and radio resources dedicated to an experiment. This definition has similarities to the concept of a Trial Network: In the case of the 6G-SANDBOX methodology, this mapping may be performed in two different ways:

1. For the use cases where a Trial Network is used, as a whole, for the purposes of executing an experiment, a Trial Network can be considered as the Slice for that particular experiment, as it fully contains the resources reserved for the experimentation.
2. In the case of Trial Networks that support multiple concurrent experiments, or where the resources of a single experiment are purposefully limited (for example, to test the effects of different limits in the performance), the subset of resources used by a single experiment execution is the Slice of that experiment.

In both cases, the underlying 6G-SANDBOX framework ensures that the resources reserved for a Trial Network are guaranteed, ensuring that the KPIs and KQIs measured during an experiment execution are not affected by concurrent events happening in other Trial Networks in the same platform. In the second case, however, it is the responsibility of the Trial Network owner to split the resources in the intended way, to guarantee the consistency of the results obtained.

2.5 EXECUTION AND DATA COLLECTION

Once an Experiment or Campaign has been defined (that is, the selection of Test Case(s), Scenario(s) and Slices(s) have been defined) and implemented (meaning that the required actions can be performed, and configurations can be applied to the components of the Trial Network), Experimenters can make use of their Trial Networks and the 6G-SANDBOX Testing Automation capabilities to repeatably run their experiments and obtain results. The 6G-SANDBOX makes some assumptions and considerations about this process in order to facilitate the production of meaningful results. In particular:

- The measurements generated by any component in a Trial Network are to be stored in a time-series database (i.e., InfluxDB). These results shall include additional metadata that allows the retrieval and filtering of the stored records at a later time, allowing the analysis of the measurements after the execution of an experiment.
- The framework will also provide information about the conditions in which the experiment has been executed. For example, a modification in the conditions of the radio performance mid-test (as may be described in a dynamic Scenario) should be recorded so that Experimenters can match the measurements at any given time with the specific conditions in the same instant.

However, Experimenters are always free to use a different selection of tools or to make use of a different methodology that the underlying Trial Network will also be able to support.

3 6G-SANDBOX TEST AND EXPERIMENT AUTOMATION (METHODOLOGY IMPLEMENTATION)

3.1 DESCRIPTION OF TEST AND EXPERIMENT AUTOMATION TOOL

This section describes the test automation tool and explains how it connects with tools and devices under test (DUTs).

3.1.1 TEST AND EXPERIMENT AUTOMATION PLATFORM

At the core of test automation in context of 6G-SANDBOX is OpenTAP [3], which has been chosen as the engine for sequencing steps and actions. By itself, OpenTAP is just a sequencer so there is a need for a framework around it to support functionalities such as realization of test cases, management of settings and parameters, execution of test cases, and management of connections to distributed infrastructure and tooling. To act as this framework, PathWave Test Automation Cloud (KS8500) (hereafter referred to as “TAC”) has been chosen, which is a fully cloud native platform for creating, managing, and running OpenTAP test plans and campaigns, and all the configurations and settings around OpenTAP plugins. The TAC is a cloudified version of PathWave Test Automation (desktop, KS8400) [4].

3.1.2 OPENTAP PLUGINS

OpenTAP is designed with a highly modular architecture where all functionalities, meaning editor, API, tool interaction, result management, etc. are added via plugins.

Figure 1 OpenTAP reference architecture modularity

Of particular interest to this project is the capability to control or interact virtually with any tool or entity through APIs, and doing so in a manner that can be sequenced and thereby automated.

A typical plugin for controlling a testing tool covers a set of features:

- **Connection settings:** As the tool or entity that is being interacted with, it is achieved via API calls and typically involves networking information. The plugin must possess information on where to establish a connection. This information may include the definition of IP and port endpoint details.
- **List of actions:** These are any actions to interact with the tool or manipulate the input (e.g., configuration files) or output (e.g., results or statistics) from the tool. The actions are defined in test steps according to OpenTAP terminology, where one step could create a session with the tool, upload a configuration file, change a parameter, run a configuration, extract results, or any other conceivable action. The granularity of the steps is defined by the developer, meaning that it is a design choice whether one step will configure the tool, run configuration and extract results simultaneously, or if these are three separate steps.

This approach allows OpenTAP to sequence actions virtually for any tool or entity (DUT, SUT, Service, etc.) that offer an API. Furthermore, there a wide range of plugins available for tools and hardware equipment available

within the 6G-SANDBOX project enabling testing and experimentation using said tools and equipment (see list in Section 4). Should there be a need to develop a plugin for another entity, the process of developing plugins is simple and can be done with very little effort. This means that there is a low barrier to connecting additional entities to the testing and experimentation automation.

3.1.3 TEST PLANS (CONCEPT IN THE TEST AUTOMATION SYSTEM)

In OpenTAP terminology, a test plan is a sequence of steps from one or more plugins, where each step is an action to interact with an entity or to manipulate an input or output. This can be seen as a realization of the test case described in section 2, but since the test plan can make use of steps from multiple plugins simultaneously, the test plan could also include actions to configure and build the scenario (also described in Section II).

Step Name	Verdict	Duration	Step Types	Command\Command
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create LoadCore Configurc			LoadCore \ Configuration Management \ Cr...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Upload Configuration to Lo			LoadCore \ Configuration Management \ U...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Create Session			LoadCore \ Session \ Create Session	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Start Test			LoadCore \ Run Test and Statistics \ Start T...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Wait for Test to Finish			LoadCore \ Run Test and Statistics \ Wait f...	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Delete Session			LoadCore \ Session \ Delete Session	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Delete Uploaded Configura			LoadCore \ Configuration Management \ D...	

Figure 2 Example of OpenTAP test plan, in this case for interacting with the tool LoadCore

The sequence which is described by the test plan is then repeatable and can be executed by the OpenTAP engine. This means that the test plan can be managed and automated via the TAC.

The steps comprising the test plan will typically take one or more parameters, which can also be exposed outside the test plan, which in turn can be saved as a preset. Multiple presets can be created for a test plan that can be subsequently selected on execution, making it easy to customize the test plan execution according to scenario or context.

3.1.4 TEST CAMPAIGNS

Where test plans are aggregating separate actions, a test campaign in TAC terminology is an aggregation of one or more test plans. The campaign allows for flow and sequence control, meaning that test plans can be executed sequentially or in parallel, but also as conditionals (e.g., if this test plan fails then run this test plan), and as parameter sweeps running through parameters exposed by the test campaign (elevated from test plans).

Figure 3 Test campaign flow example

The test campaigns provide a higher level of abstraction compared to the test plans; that is, a test campaign is aimed towards collecting network performance KPIs while the individual test plans within the campaign evaluate throughput, delay, packets, etc.

The parameters exposed by the test plans in the campaign can again be made available at the campaign level. Also, here it is possible to create presets of the parameters and the presets can be selected upon execution of the campaign to easily customize the execution to the specific scenario and context.

3.1.5 RUNNERS

The OpenTAP runner is a plugin installed with OpenTAP which handles the connection and interaction with the TAC. This is done by registering the runner with the TAC and waiting for tasks (test plan execution) to be assigned to the runner. The runner initiates the contact to the TAC meaning that the runner only requires an internet connection to function besides access to the entities it should interact with.

Figure 4 Conceptual deployment and interactions of the OpenTAP Runner

Deployment of the runner can be done manually using an installer or via a command line interface – both options are described and information is provided in the TAC UI. Since the runner is an OpenTAP plugin, the only prerequisite is that OpenTAP has been installed in advance.

The deployment of the runner can also be automated in various ways. For example, it can be deployed as a container using Helm charts for K8s or as a docker container via Docker-compose. Likewise, it is possible to automate the deployment using scripts for Ansible, Terraform, or any other deployment automation tool. In both cases, the command line commands described in the TAC UI can be used – specifically the registration token is important to ensure that the runner is registered to the correct realm in the TAC.

The deployment of the runner in the trial network is the initial installation process. Integration occurs when the deployed runner is connected to the trial network, and its components are configured to work seamlessly with other elements in the network.

Once the runner is deployed, the TAC offers APIs (same as used for the UI) for configuring settings of the runner, installing plugins, and sharing access to the runner with other users within the same TAC realm.

3.2 REALIZATION OF TEST CASE, SCENARIO, AND SLICE

3.2.1 REALIZATION OF TEST CASES USING OPENTAP TEST PLANS

As described in Section 3.1.3, the OpenTAP test plan can be seen as a realization of the Test Case Definition described in Section 2.2. The test plan consists of steps that carry out the actions described in the textual description of the test case. This can include both verifying preconditions if possible, configuring and generating test traffic, extract statistics and results needed for KPI evaluation and validation, and post-processing of extracted information if possible. The preconditions might not be verifiable via interaction with tools or entities that can be interacted with through OpenTAP plugins, in which case the preconditions must be verified through other means (e.g., manually). Likewise, the post-processing of results and statistics might not be possible to perform via OpenTAP plugins, in which case the post-processing must be done by other means. But whether the post-processing can be covered or not, it is important that information extracted from the test or experiment be stored for later inspection or be made available for additional post-processing.

For the actions of configuring and generating test traffic, or performing any other action with a tool, DUT, or other entity, it is handled via functionalities offered by OpenTAP plugins. This means that for the actions to be possible to perform, the entity should expose the actions via an API for the plugins to consume.

The extraction of results is a feature that is very well supported by the TAC, in the sense that the plugins interacting with tools or other entities should extract and publish results and statistics. Once done the TAC will collect the extracted results and statistics and store them as an artifact of the run.

3.2.2 REALIZATION OF SCENARIO AND SLICES USING TRIAL NETWORK OR PART OF THAT TRIAL NETWORK AND RESOURCES AVAILABLE TO THE EXPERIMENT

In the methodology, Scenarios and Slices define the conditions in which an experiment is executed, which can have an effect in the measurements and observed performance of the system under test. During experimentation, this can be seen as the usage of different configurations in the radio equipment (Scenarios) and the scaling of the available resources (Slices).

Experimenting under a particular Scenario, then, consists in the configuration of the correct set of parameters in every component of the radio equipment that is part of the Trial Network. It is important to consider the capabilities of each Trial Network, since a particular Trial Network may not possibly be configured in such a way that matches the conditions defined in a Scenario.

Prior to, or during the execution of the test sequence defined in a Test Case, an experimenter can make use of the relevant APIs (either directly or through the use of OpenTAP DUTs and Instruments) to apply the necessary settings, as required for implementing the selected Scenario.

In the case of the Slices, the Trial Network owner may define the availability of resources in two different ways:

1. The Trial Network contains exactly the resources defined in the Scenario. In this case, the Trial Network is limited to a single Scenario (and a single experiment any given time) but may be used for experiments with different combinations of Test Cases and Scenarios.
2. The Trial Network contains enough resources to run multiple experiments at the same time, or to artificially constrain the resources so that the same Test Case and Scenario pair can be tested under

different conditions (e.g., two different Slices, one where the full Trial Network represents the best conditions and a second one where the system under test can only make use of half the resources). For the first case, an Experimenter would use the Slice description as a guide for creating a Trial Network Descriptor with the same resources, using it to run combinations of Test Cases and Scenarios as desired. Since the number of resources are fixed, it is not necessary to perform any additional actions regarding the Slice. In the second option, it is responsibility of the Trial Network owner to ensure that the resources are correctly distributed, in order to avoid affecting the validity of the results.

3.3 HOW TO TRIGGER TEST OR EXPERIMENT EXECUTION FROM CLOUD PLATFORM

Once an experiment or test has been defined and realized through OpenTAP test plans and test campaigns, the TAC platform allows for different options for triggering the execution of test campaigns. These options are described in the following subsections.

3.3.1 MANUAL TRIGGERING

A campaign can be triggered to execute from the TAC UI by selecting the campaign and clicking the run button. Then the presets to be used can be selected and the execution can be started.

Figure 5 Triggering of selected campaign manually via “Play” button, or via “Schedule” button

3.3.2 SCHEDULED TRIGGERING

The TAC offers a scheduler functionality for planning when to trigger execution of campaigns. The scheduler allows for setting a time and date for when to execute the campaign and to set a name for the schedule. Furthermore, the execution can be made recurring with a periodicity on the scale of hours, days, weeks, months, and years. It can also be set to execute a fixed number of times.

Figure 6 Scheduler of the Test Automation Cloud Platform for scheduling campaign execution

3.3.3 TRIGGERING VIA NORTH BOUND API (CI/CD INTEGRATION)

To support integration between the TAC and automation tools such as CI/CD tools and service or network orchestrators, the TAC offers a north bound API. This is a REST API defined according to the OpenAPI v3 specification. At the time of this writing, the offered functionality is limited to the following:

- Listing campaigns available
- Listing versions of a specific campaign
- Listing previously started runs
- Showing status of a specific run
- Triggering execution of a campaign

Figure 7 Swagger representation of the OpenAPI specification of the north bound API

More features will be added here, such as selecting specific preset of the campaign.

3.4 INTERACTION WITH TRIAL NETWORK

The interaction with the Trial network is enabled via the Trial Network Life-Cycle Management (TNLCM). The description of the TNLCM, its design and its API are all described in the 6G-SANDBOX Deliverable D4.1 to which we refer to. The document will be published by the end of January 2024.

4 TESTING AND MEASUREMENT EQUIPMENT IN 6G-SANDBOX PLATFORMS

The 6G-SANDBOX facility offers a wide range of tooling and equipment to support virtually any form of evaluation or validation work on top of the infrastructure (network, components, and equipment). This is an addition to the trial network and 6G library described and developed in the project. But the tools and equipment are not just stand-alone entities that can be used in connection with experiments. They are integrated into the platforms and into the 6G library to function as integrated components of the larger system (6G-SANDBOX facility). This means that components of tools (such as probes, endpoints, agents, load modules, etc.) can be deployed as part of the trial network for a specific experiment. But also, that the tools provide support to any trial or experiment in performing measurements and performance evaluation, traffic and signal capture, noise or neighbouring load generation, security evaluation, and much more. Overall, the 6G-SANDBOX facility is a very well-equipped testbed for any type of experimentation, trial, or evaluation related to 6G and 6G-enabling technologies.

The following sections contain descriptions of the available tools and equipment, divided into solutions comprising hardware components and pure software solutions. Additionally, a table is provided showing which tools and equipment are available in which sites at the time of the writing of this document.

4.1 PHYSICAL TESTING EQUIPMENT

By Physical testing equipment we refer to equipment that have a dedicated physical platform needed to run the capability. Most of these equipment can be shipped from facility to facility to enable experimentations.

4.1.1.1 WAVEJUDGE

Wavejudge Wireless Analyzer Solutions are a set of over-the-air monitor toolsets that offer users real-time visibility of the interactions between the physical and protocol layers in wireless transmissions. [5] These analyzers allow for wireless conditions to be captured in the field and then replayed in the lab, allowing for the evaluation of the impacts of said conditions on MIMO, beamforming, and scheduling. This also enables the verification of base station behaviour in terms of the over-the-air interface, including complex modulation schemes and antenna structures. All of this allows for a holistic understanding of the interactions between any user equipment and the base station at all layers, thus enabling the user to identify complex interoperability issues and improve the performance of the overall wireless connection.

4.1.1.2 UESIM

UeSim (SW), DUSim, CUSim enable infrastructure vendors, chipset providers and mobile operators to validate end-to-end Radio Access Network performance by emulating real network traffic over both radio and O-RAN fronthaul interfaces. [6] The systems have been designed to accelerate multi-standard end-to-end network verification by generating IP traffic load, simulating applications running on thousands of concurrent devices operating real voice and data sessions. Both conducted and live testing across the full range of frequencies are supported, with the possibility to cover real-world scenarios spanning protocol and load testing in the lab to field testing, trials, and deployments.

UeSim (HW part) in addition to the software part of the UeSim tool here is also deployed the hardware box to provide hardware acceleration. It connects to the gNB to emulate thousands of users and perform load testing.

4.1.1.3 DUSIM

DuSIM validates O-CU functionality by emulating traffic over the midhaul interface, providing vital assistance to infrastructure vendors, chipset providers and mobile operators operating in the O-RAN context. [7] These capabilities are scalable to the tune of hundreds of O-DUs, and thousands of UEs and are available for work with both the NSA and SA topologies. Thousands of sessions can be simulated across multiple coordinated emulated O-DUs and the impairment capabilities allow for negative scenarios to be tested as well. Each UE can have

multiple activities, and the objective for each L7 activity can be configured for any given UE. DuSIM itself is lightweight and can be run on standard COTS hardware or in container form on the Cloud.

4.1.1.4 RUSIM

RuSIM enables infrastructure vendors, chipset providers, and mobile operators to easily perform functional, conformance, and performance testing of O-RAN distributed units (O-DUs) over fronthaul functional split option 7.2x. [8] Fully scalable and virtualized, the solution runs on commercial, off-the-shelf Intel servers without the need for layer-1 hardware accelerators or special-purpose hardware and offers a migration path to the Cloud. RuSIM enables you to verify the network by generating internet protocol (IP) traffic load. The solution simulates applications running on thousands of concurrent devices with real voice and data sessions. You can assess the full protocol stack for 4G and 5G New Radio (NR) for both non-standalone (NSA) and standalone (SA) architectures over the enhanced Common Public Radio Interface (eCPRI).

CoreSIM is a 4G/5G core simulator, and makes Radio Access Network testing easier by eliminating Core Network unwanted dependencies and by allowing an easily controllable, repeatable test environment setup. RAN test efforts can thus be concentrated on the Device Under Test, speeding up 3GPP standards implementation. Highly scalable, CoreSIM allows up to a hundred independent test lines in parallel. An ePC simulator is available for NSA wrap-around and a 5G core simulator for SA wrap-around. Data, storage, voice, and video protocols are supported. It is possible to host CoreSIM on any Intel server.

4.1.1.5 CUSIM

CuSIM validates O-DU functionality by emulating traffic over the midhaul interface. [9] in companion to the UeSIM and RuSIM software packages, CuSIM can support hundreds of O-DUs and simulate complex subscriber behaviour and application traffic flows. When combined with the aforementioned packages, a complete wraparound test for an O-DU can be performed. CuSIM supports realistic traffic mixes through either its built-in generator or the option to use IP passthrough, and any results and statistics can be viewed in real time alongside post-processing data.

4.1.1.6 N6705 DC POWER ANALYZER

The N6705C DC Power Analyzer provides unrivalled productivity gains for sourcing and measuring DC voltage and current into the DUT. [10] The tool is modular in design and has the capabilities of up to four advanced power supplies — plus a built-in digital multimeter (DMM), scope, arb, and data logger.

4.1.1.7 O-RAN STUDIO FOR RU TESTING

O-RAN Studio for O-RU testing (HW part): Open RAN Studio includes powerful O-RAN focused tools to construct, play, capture, and measure O-RAN traffic over 10 Gbps to 25 Gbps (fronthaul) Ethernet interfaces. [11] Out-of-the-box integration with Keysight's industry leading PathWave Signal Generation for 5G NR and 89600 VSA software enables sophisticated 5G and LTE signal creation and easy capture, extraction, and export of IQ vectors – for advanced modulation analysis of received RF / mmWave signals and radio performance. Additionally, when combined with Keysight spectrum analysers and signal sources, the integrated Open RAN Studio solution delivers the most comprehensive cross domain, multi-channel RF / mmWave and O-RAN protocol measurements available in the industry, for both FR1 and FR2 radios, downlink (DL) and uplink (UL) paths.

4.1.1.8 UXM 5G E7515B

UXM (HW): The E7515B UXM 5G is a highly integrated signalling test platform with multiformat stack support, rich processing power, and abundant RF resources. [12] Supporting the latest 3GPP Release 16 and early R17, the E7515B UXM 5G wireless test solution enables a 5G call with a device under test (DUT) in different 5G New Radio (NR) deployment modes; non-stand-alone (NSA), stand-alone (SA), and frequency bands FR1 and FR2. The solution performs signalling test for device RF characteristics, protocol compliance, and functional key performance indicators. It also supports LTE, eMTC, and C-V2X signalling formats.

4.1.1.9 VXG MICROWAVE SIGNAL GENERATOR

VXG Vector Signal Generators are a high-end solution for millimetre wave signal generation applications. [13] Offering best in class output power and ultra-low phase noise, these generators are well suited to even the most demanding wireless applications. With a frequency range of 9 kHz to 110 GHz and a modulation bandwidth of 5 GHz, the VXG system can work with even the most demanding signals. The Direct Digital Synthesis (DDS) architecture allows for substantial improvements in phase noise and extremely fine frequency tuning resolutions. Up to 8 transmitters can be emulated simultaneously on each of the four channels, and the channels can be used in MIMO configurations with multipath and fading models for 5G NR performance tests.

4.1.1.10 AC POWER ANALYZER

The PA2203 IntegraVision Power Analyzer allows for voltage, current, and power traces to be shown for four distinct channels in real time. [14] The high-speed digitizer allows for the visualisation of in-rush currents and state changes, while the continuous whole cycle analysis allows for measurement without any discontinuities or gaps.

4.1.1.11 MTRX 32 CHANNEL

The E6464A Multi Transceiver RF Test Set provides up to 64 VSA and up to 64 VSG in one instrument. [15] Highly scalable and featuring an advanced digital MIMO and massive MIMO signal weighing matrix, it is purpose built to support beamforming measurements in these contexts.

4.1.1.12 NEMO WIRELESS

Keysight's Nemo Network solutions improve the user experience and the quality of a network in a cost-effective way leveraging optimised and automated processes. In this case, three key parts of the Nemo ecosystem will be implemented. The Nemo Handy Handheld Measurement Solution is an Android application that measures wireless diagnostics information with regard to the air interface and QoS/QoE (Quality of Service / Quality of Experience) for mobile applications. [16] With support for the latest wireless technologies, Nemo Handy is ideal for in-building measurements with indoor positioning and mapping features that work automatically and significantly reduce the amount of time taken to perform measurements. Multiple actual services can be tested and compared from an end user perspective with the ability to record a series of touch inputs as part of a script that can be run automatically. A higher understanding of the performance in these cases can be achieved with the Nemo Outdoor NR Drive Test Solution. Allowing for the measure of real user QoE and supporting all stages of the mobile network lifecycle, the collected data can be subjected to comprehensive post-processing to analyse and glean subtle insights. [17] It is inherently scalable and allows for the connection of up to 60 smartphones to one laptop with support for the latest models and other IoT devices on the market. Network quality for end users can be ensured no matter what device they use, as Nemo Outdoor offers KPIs for the widest range of 5G NR equipment on the market. Further post-processing and analyses for any data gathered can be done using the Nemo Analyze Drive Test Post Processing Solution. Capable of powerful post-processing, troubleshooting and statistical reporting, it completes the data chain provided by the other two Nemo tools in use. Featuring best in class visualisation, fully customisable KPIs and reporting, full automation for the processing chain and up to date support for all 3GPP network technologies, Analyze allows for versatile and seamless post processing integration. [18]

4.1.1.13 PNAX VECTOR NETWORK ANALYZER

The PNA-X is the most advanced Vector Network Analyzer in the industry space. It is also an integrated and flexible microwave test engine for measuring amplifiers, mixers, frequency converters, and other active devices. The hardware itself comprises of two internal signal sources, a combiner, S-parameter and noise receivers, pulse modulators and generators, and a flexible set of switches and RF access points. Together, these components provide a basis for a broad range of linear and nonlinear measurements, with a single set of connections to your device under test. The wide range of possibilities means the PNA-X acts to replace an entire racks worth of

equipment. Measurement applications for the PNA-X include S-parameters, Gain compression, intermodulation, conversion gain/loss, antenna testing, and many other applications.

4.1.1.14 NETWORK EMULATOR 3

The Network Emulator 3 from Keysight Technologies is a precision test instrument for Ethernet impairment emulation at various speeds from 10GE to 100GE. [19] It allows users to accurately emulate the real network conditions that occur over live production LAN/WAN networks and test the performance and interoperability of new hardware, protocols, and applications. The device has a modular appliance design with one or two impairment engines per card and a flexible resource management feature. It supports transparent emulation of delays and impairments for any higher-layer L2/7 protocols and optical media physical layer clock transparency for SyncE support. The device can be used for various use cases such as 5G delay and impairment testing, corporate LAN/WAN emulation, server consolidation/migration, application cloud migration and storage extension, wireless/mobile delay and impairment simulation, satellite network delay emulation, and more.

4.2 SOFTWARE BASED TESTING SOLUTIONS

4.2.1.1 HAWKEYE

Hawkeye is an active network performance monitoring platform which can be used for QoS monitoring, application and web monitoring, Wi-Fi monitoring, cloud monitoring, etc. [20] It is a web-based platform for multi-user access, test scheduling, data storage, and real-time analysis. It can effectively validate network performance, isolate problems, and proactively detect issues by running scheduled verification tests. Hawkeye supports a variety of service level agreement (SLA) and quality of experience (QoE) objectives. It takes control of user experience with real-time QoS monitoring. It can proactively detect, diagnose, and fix performance problems by deploying software and hardware endpoints to any network location. It can be used to verify virtual infrastructure, validate deployments by simulating live network traffic, and monitor distributed networks from core to edge. The synthetic monitoring traffic can be generated up to 10G links. In addition, the tool leverages machine learning to quickly pinpoint outliers and prioritize fixes.

4.2.1.2 BREAKINGPOINTVE

BreakingPoint Virtual Edition (VE) is a security testing tool for performing penetration testing on network infrastructure. [21] It generates scalable real-world traffic for complete performance and security testing, and it validates both virtual and physical devices using a complete test software solution. The tool features an HTML5 web-based user interface and REST API support for test configuration and execution, and it runs on private cloud platforms including VMware ESXi, KVM hypervisors and VMware vCenter, and OpenStack orchestration. BreakingPoint supports all major Public Cloud providers such as Amazon AWS, Google Cloud Platform, and Microsoft Azure.

4.2.1.3 IXNETWORK VE

IxNetwork Virtual Edition (VE) is a virtualized network performance testing solution that emulates a wide range of networking protocols and traffic types. [22] It can test physical and virtual network infrastructures and devices, with the ability to validate conformance, functionality, performance, scalability, and convergence. IxNetwork VE can be deployed in various environments, such as standalone hypervisors, private clouds, public clouds, and containers. It supports different network connection modes, such as virtual switch, PCI-PT, and SR-IOV. It also provides powerful traffic generation and analysis capabilities, with DPDK Performance Acceleration for L23 Traffic and hundreds of application traffic flows for Stateful L47 Traffic.

4.2.1.4 IXLOAD VE

IxLoad Virtual Edition (VE) is a virtualized multiplay services testing solution that delivers comprehensive functional and performance testing to validate user quality of experience (QoE) in physical and virtual networks. [23] IxLoad VE emulates web, video, voice, storage, VPN, wireless, infrastructure, and security protocols to

create realistic scenarios. It provides a flexible traffic generation and analysis solution to validate physical and virtual applications and networks. A modular system design enables the ability to deploy virtual test ports inside virtualized network devices and allows IxLoad VE to elastically scale with the cloud infrastructure. It provides real-time QoE metrics to quickly identify network degradations and isolate breaking points. IxLoad VE supports a wide variety of fully stateful protocols to emulate a complete multiplayer user environment. It delivers a sophisticated subscriber modelling capability that enables users to replicate the dynamic nature of subscriber behaviour. It also includes AppLibrary, an extensive library of pre-defined application flows that simulate end-user interactions and devices. It also supports different network connection modes such as virtual switch, PCI-PT, or SR-IOV.

4.2.1.5 CLOUDPEAK

CloudPeak allows the user to validate and benchmark VMware vCenter and OpenStack-based private clouds and can run evaluations on a testbed for a single compute node or large environments with many racks. [24] It supports the ability to individually validate the compute/network/storage performance dimensions, by measuring VIM performance using custom VM instantiation and VM termination test methodology. The tool contains predefined test scenarios for NFVI validation and is able to validate from a VNF or network perspective through real workload and powerful traffic emulation. It also includes industry-proven workload emulation from the OPNFV Yardstick portfolio. The tool also supports measuring the scheduler's capability to isolate the good workloads and the bad noisy neighbors, and measure the performance impact of VNF instantiation and VNF workloads in the presence of (noisy) neighbors.

4.2.1.6 CYPERF

CyPerf supports the creation of digital twin of users, applications, and attacks to replicate and test QoE in real-world network environments. [25] It also natively supports authentication and can send application and security traffic over authenticated sessions at high scale. The tool is highly scalable and supports emulating millions of concurrent users and millions of connections per second that elastically scale up and down, enabling both resiliency and chaos testing. The agents of the tool are containerized and deployed as lightweight traffic agents or pods on-prem, as VMs, as managed Kubernetes deployments, private or public cloud (AWS, GCP, Azure). It supports both lab and live network testing for test pf performance and security both pre-deployment in a lab or safely in live production networks.

4.2.1.7 THREAT SIMULATOR

Threat Simulator is a breach and attack simulation platform that provides enterprise security teams with insights into the effectiveness of their security posture and actionable intelligence to improve it. [26] It is a flexible, cloud-based breach and attack simulation platform that scales with the size of the network. The light, container-based, infrastructure-agnostic software agents enable operations on-premises, on private and public clouds, and on remote user laptops. It is featured with fully managed "Dark Cloud" infrastructure, which can simulate external adversaries, malicious nodes, and C&C servers in the public domain. It has built-in integration with top network security controls and SIEM tools, and has a diversified library of MITRE ATT&CK techniques and threat vectors to validate network, endpoint and email security controls. The out-of-the-box attack library enables the users to simulate the full Cyber Kill Chain® for popular breaches, relevant software threats, and Advanced Persistent Threats (APTs). The tool supports built in packet capture and enables continuous security assessments across the enterprise-wide network.

4.2.1.8 LOADCORE

LoadCore test solution addresses the testing and validation of 5G elements in the core network. [27] It can simulate UE behaviour in various 5G use case deployments, including network slicing, multi-access edge computing (MEC) low latency and offloading, video optimization. The service quality validation with subscriber modelling, multiplayer traffic generation, and quality of experience (QoE) measurements can be performed. The tool can be used to validate complex scenarios for service-based architectures, multiple user-plane QoS

characteristics per flow or session, as well as 5G nodes and interfaces. The test can be scaled up to millions of subscribers using stateful application traffic mixes that can interact with real servers and peers. Control test traffic mix and intensity can be applied using network objectives to independently manage control- and user-planes. In addition, the tool is available for deployment on all major public clouds, including AWS Marketplace (both BYOL and PAYG options).

4.2.1.9 EXATA

EXata is a platform with more than 20 years in the market for the digital twin. [28] It is a discrete event simulation platform that allows modelling and performance evaluation of local area networks (LAN), wide area networks (WAN), wireless networks and communication protocols. EXata is used to design, develop, and optimize communication networks and systems in various fields, such as telecommunications, Internet of Things (IoT), mobile networks, autonomous vehicles, and defence systems. The tool provides a realistic and accurate simulation environment, allowing users to evaluate network behaviour and performance in different scenarios. EXata has the capability to model a wide variety of communication protocols, including 3G/4G/5G and soon 6G components as part of the development of the various European projects that Keysight is part of (e.g., SNS JU 6G-SANDBOX and IMAGINE-B5G).

Keysight Technologies offers a comprehensive suite of 5G network modelling and simulation solutions to help evaluate the performance and behavior of 5G cellular networks. Keysight's 5G Model Library includes high-fidelity models that implement the enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) functionality of the 5G standard, such as massive MIMO, beamforming, network slicing, and edge computing. Keysight's 5G models support both non-standalone (NSA) and standalone (SA) modes of deployment, as well as frequency division duplex (FDD) and time division duplex (TDD) in FR1 (≤ 6 GHz) and FR2 (≥ 24 GHz) bands. Keysight's

The EXata network simulator and emulator platform provides an intuitive, easy-to-use GUI for creating simulation scenarios of a variety of communication networks, including 5G. The GUI supports drag-and-drop functionality to create networks using pre-configured high-fidelity models of devices and links, as well as importing terrain data in several widely used formats. The GUI also provides models of different types of applications that can run over cellular networks, such as voice, video streaming, email, messaging, web browsing, etc. To more accurately mimic a real-world mix of applications in a simulation scenario, EXata also provides tools to capture traffic from existing cellular networks and wireless LANs that can be used in 5G network simulations.

4.2.1.10 CLOUDLENS

CloudLens is a complete cloud-based visibility solution for virtual network traffic. [29] It allows the user to capture, filter, and forward traffic between virtual machines, containers or Kubernetes Pods, and tools. It also provides packet processing capabilities such as aggregation, deduplication, application filtering, and NetFlow generation within the cloud. CloudLens supports multiple platforms and environments such as AWS, Azure, GCP, VMware, KVM, and more. It can scale elastically with cloud instances and offers a user-friendly interface and dashboard.

4.2.1.11 PATHWAVE SYSTEM DESIGN (SYSTEMVUE)

SystemVue offers the most advanced prototyping and design platform for complex RF systems with faster simulation speed, near-circuit fidelity, libraries for radar, electronic warfare, satellite, 5G, and WiFi, plus enterprise integration with numerous partners. [30]

PathWave System Design is a software platform that enables RF system architects, designers, and verification teams to create and simulate complex RF systems with high accuracy and speed. It offers multi-domain modelling and simulation, RF-aware tools, real-world libraries, measurement science, and integration with enterprise design and verification tools. PathWave System Design can be licensed in bundles with different simulation capabilities and supports MATLAB and Simulink integration.

4.2.1.12 RICTEST

RICtest emulates O-RAN network nodes and traffic profiles on different RAN Intelligent Controller's (RIC's) interfaces, allowing testing of the Near Real-Time RIC (and of xApps it hosts) and of the Non-Real-Time RIC (and of rApps it hosts). [31] This simulation tool has the capability of simulating E2 nodes that are serving a large number of UEs distributed across multiple cells with mobility and traffic. The capability to simulate configurable traffic patterns and handover scenarios is very important to test xApps hosted on RICs. RICtest emulates thousands of CUs and DUs over the E2 interface, allowing for testing of Near-Real-Time RIC and of xApps hosted on RIC.

4.3 MEASUREMENT EQUIPMENT AVAILABILITY IN 6G-SANDBOX PLATFORMS

All the tools and equipment listed in previous sections are available in the 6G-SANDBOX facilities, but some of the items are only available in some facilities initially due to availability. Additionally, due to practicalities of deploying tools or equipment, more and more will become available in the sites over time.

The document "Experimenter Facility Capability Overview 1.0" [32] contains an overview of the KPI measurements status in the different facilities. This document is regularly updated to guide interested experimenters. It provides the view on the current status and availability of measurement equipment across the 6G-SANDBOX facilities.

5 6G-SANDBOX TESTING REPORTING (6G KPI & KVI REPOSITORY)

5.1 TRIAL NETWORK MONITORING SYSTEM

The 6G-SANDBOX platform requires an efficient way of fast prototyping for new features, followed by an effective testing plan. For the latter, different application modules will be implemented on the experimental platform to obtain real results. The best way to analyze those results in a systematic way is the collection of Key Performance Indicators (KPI), numeric values measured automatically in the platform, which can be displayed and compared in a sequence of successive tests, alone or in combination with other KPIs. At a higher level, the tested applications provide final experiences that can be evaluated from system or even user perspective. This experience can also be measured with Key Value Indicators (KVI) that, although a harder to obtain, eventually yield to numeric values that can be stored.

In this section, we will describe the architecture of the repository for application-level KPIs and KVIs that will be used in 6G-SANDBOX. It can gather data from different modules, storing them and providing a practical and efficient mechanism to be retrieved, analyzed, and displayed.

The design of this repository has been done with the following requirements in mind:

- KPI/KVI may be any numerical or text-based data. The repository just provides a way of storing and retrieving them, with no analysis done internally.
- Data is stored in a persistent storage system, with redundancy. As 6G-SANDBOX is an experimental facility, no high availability is fully guaranteed, though.
- System should support peaks of up to 10 new values of each KPI/KVI per second, although the expected average update period is around 10 seconds.
- Third Party modules (external to the platform owner) will provide the KPI/KVIs in real time through a programmatic API.
- Data providers will have access to the data they provide only, data from other providers will not be available for them.
- System will automatically collect KPIs from the platform itself. In this case no additional integration will be required from third parties.
- A visualization engine (based on Grafana) will be included in the platform, accessible to the platform owner only.

A high-level view of the repository architecture is depicted in the following figure:

Figure 8 High-level view of the repository architecture

The “platform” area in the above figure includes all servers which are co-located in the main platform site, and which have direct IP visibility. The modules listed in the figure are:

- **Database:** the InfluxDB database which stores the KPI/KVI data
<https://www.influxdata.com/products/influxdb/>
- **Telegraf agent:** a software module (a daemon) running in one or more servers within the platform. It should include a plugin for InfluxDB. Several telegraf agents may be running concurrently in different servers. At least one of them should include a UDP interface for receiving messages with KPI/KVIs from other application modules in the platform.
<https://www.influxdata.com/time-series-platform/telegraf/>
- **Applications,** running within the platform or externally on third-party servers.
- **NaC server:** this server centralizes the operation of the Network as Code architecture. It communicates externally with the third-party applications and implements the functionality. For the operation of the repository, it implements the communication with the database to store and retrieve the data required by the API.
- **Grafana:** this server retrieves information from the Database and generates real time graphs that can be displayed from a web browser
<https://grafana.com/>
- **Browser:** a standard web browser for visualizing Grafana outputs. It is only available within the platform.

The core of the repository is an InfluxDB database which receives real time data from multiple external sources and stores them persistently. InfluxDB is an open-source time-series database designed to manage and store time-stamped data, the kind of data common in applications such as system monitoring, performance analysis, application logs or telemetry. The retention policies in InfluxDB can be configured to define how long data should

be stored and with what granularity. It is designed to provide high-performance capabilities, thanks to an inverted index mechanism and an efficient caching.

The database runs on a dedicated server, installed in a Virtual Machine with Linux OS. This server is accessible directly through IP from all internal servers in the platform. This server is also running the Grafana server, which provides an HTTP API for visualization of data in a browser.

There are two levels of access to the repository:

1. **Internal:** applications and system modules belonging to the platform. These modules may have direct access to the database for storage. The platform operator has also unlimited access to the database for data retrieval, including the visualization of data through the built-in Grafana service.
2. **External:** third party applications running out of the platform deliver data to the repository using a provided library with a programmatic interface (Network as Code paradigm). The functions in this API provide both storage and retrieval of data. In this case each third party has only access to the data that he has provided.

All servers in the platform are expected to run a Telegraf agent which gathers operational information (CPU/GPU usage, network usage, energy, etc.) and sends it to the repository using an InfluxDB plugin. Other servers in the platform may provide specific KPI/KVIs through UDP to a Telegraf agent, which therefore acts as a proxy. In this case the format of the data is free (text based).

The repository is installed within the platform, in a trusted environment. Therefore, access control and data protection are guaranteed by the common platform architecture, as any other server. The external access to the repository from third party applications is always done using the provided NaC library, which uses a REST interface for the actual delivery of data. The usage of this interface (including discovery and authentication) is controlled by the CAPIF module in the platform.

5.2 OPERATION

5.2.1 INSTALLATION

The API for third parties is based on the Network as Code paradigm. In its current version it is delivered as a python library which should be used within the third-party application. Python 3 must be used, and it is recommended to install the Python wheel library file in a clean environment, preferably a new virtual environment.

5.2.2 EXPERIMENT KPI COLLECTION

KPI/KVI may be ingested into the repository through different paths:

1. **Platform KPIs:** the performance indicators from the servers installed within the platform are injected directly into the repository, using a preconfigured format. They will be accessible by the platform owner.
2. **Internal modules:** application modules running on servers within the platform can also send KPI/KVI data directly to the repository. In this case the format is free. Retrieval can be done using a programmatic interface in the form of a REST API (GET to query data, POST to write)
3. **External modules:** applications running outside of the platform infrastructure can deliver KPI/KVIs with arbitrary formats and later retrieve the data using an external API. The internal communication is done using a RESTful protocol (IP connectivity required), but for the application a python API is provided.

5.2.3 EXPERIMENT KPI QUERY

The platform owner has full access to all KPI/KVI data stored in the repository. Data can be retrieved using the standard InfluxDB protocol, but the typical usage within the platform will be accessing the provided Grafana

interface. This front-end retrieves data from the database and presents it in configurable panels, so the platform owner can monitor it permanently in a very easy way.

Figure 9 Grafana front end to visualize KPIs

The external users of the repository can use the provided NaC interface (python based) to query the database and retrieve subsets of the data that they have previously inserted. This path does not provide access to data from other users, or to the platform KPIs.

5.3 API (PYTHON)

5.3.1 APPLICATION KPI SUBMIT

The following function will send a KPI value to the repository:

```
KPI_send(<KPI_family>, <KPI_id>, <KPI_value>)
```

Where:

- KPI_family is a text string identifying a set of related KPIs (defined by the app)
- KPI_id is the unique identifier of the KPI (defined by the app), also a text string
- KPI_value is a text string containing a comma separated assignment of <id>=<val> describing with the KPI, format is free.

Considerations:

- The time at which the function is called will be automatically stored, associated with the value.
- The identifiers do not need to be declared in advance.

Example:

```
KPI_send("AGV_KPIs", "agv1", "speed=3,bitrate=34,latency=67")
```

```
KPI_send("AGV_KPIs", "agv7", "speed=2,bitrate=34,latency=17")
```

This will store two new values of KPIs “agv1” and “agv7” (probably corresponding to two different physical AGVs) with values for fields speed, bitrate, and latency. Both KPIs (agv1 and agv7) belong to the same family AGV_KPIs.

5.3.2 APPLICATION KPI RETRIEVAL

The following functions retrieve KPI values from the repository:

- Retrieve the KPI values corresponding to indicated time range:

```
KPI_get(<KPI_family>, <KPI_id>, <tstamp_beg>, <tstamp_end>)
```

- Retrieve the KPI values stored before a specific moment:

```
KPI_last-before_get(<KPI_family>, <KPI_id>, <tstamp>)
```

- Retrieve the last KPI value that was stored:

```
KPI_last_get(<KPI_family>, <KPI_id>)
```

Where:

- KPI_family is a text string identifying a set of related KPIs (defined by the app)
- KPI_id is the unique identifier of the KPI (defined by the app), also a text string
- Timestamps are strings defining a time (local time) in the format "YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS"

Examples:

```
KPI_get("AGV_KPIs", "agv1", "2023-11-15 13:01:10", "2023-11-15 14:01:10")
```

```
KPI_last-before_get("AGV_KPIs", "agv1", "2023-11-15 13:01:10")
```

```
KPI_last_get("AGV_KPIs", "agv1")
```

Returned value will be a text array with CSV format and this structure:

- First line: tags of KPI family columns in the database. First column will always be "time", indicating the timestamp when the value was stored.
- Each line after first one contains a CSV with the values (quoted) of the fields tagged in the first line. If a value is missing, it will be empty (two commas without anything in the middle). Time value is provided in ISO 8601 format.

Example of returned value:

```
KPI_get("AGV_KPIs", "agv1", "2023-11-16 12:40:38", "2023-11-16 12:40:45")
```

```
"time","KPI1","KPI2","KPI3","KPI_Video","host","object"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:38.625782967Z",3,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:39.628658116Z",4,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:40.631526924Z",5,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:41.633802248Z",6,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:42.636565157Z",7,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:43.639478904Z",8,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:44.642400956Z",9,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"  
"2023-11-16T12:40:45.645207054Z",10,34,67,,,"upv-tig","agv1"
```

6 6G-SANDBOX KPI & KVI MEASUREMENT IMPLEMENTATION

6.1 INFRASTRUCTURE AND TRIAL NETWORK EVALUATION

6.1.1 KPI EVALUATION

Based on the KPIs as identified and defined in D2.1 [1] there will be a number of test plans created to automate the process of evaluating said KPIs within the 6G-SANDBOX project. Practically the KPI evaluation will be done with a tool or a combination of tools which is/are selected based on what features and area the tool covers.

The following describes the initial set of test plans created and which KPIs they evaluate. The intention is to continuously for the duration of the project create such test plans and make them available to project partners and experimenters.

Note that the test plans listed below are what is available at the time of this writing, meaning more will be created and made available – both for the same tools but also for other tools. Furthermore, the list of test plans given here are only the set that has been chosen to be created centrally in the project, meaning that any partner or experimenter can create whatever test plan, evaluating any KPI using any available tool.

6.1.1.1 HAWKEYE TEST PLANS

Adaptive Video: Video KPIs

This test plan generates results for Avg Video Playback Rate(bps), Avg Video Pre-Buffering Duration(ms), Jitter Buffer Full Count, Jitter Buffer Full Duration(ms), Video Playback Downshifts, Video Playback Upshifts, Video Quality, Video Stopped Count and Video Stopped Duration(ms).

Network KPI: Packet Loss, Latency and Voice MOS

Network KPI Test, Produces results: Packet Loss Rate, Packet Loss Burst, One Way Delay(ms), Jitter(ms), Max Jitter(ms), Max Delay Variation(ms), Voice MOS Score.

Video Stream: Video MDI Scores

This test plan generates Video MDI Scores.

Throughput: TCP/UDP Single/Multi stream Throughput

These test plans find the throughput for TCP and UDP in both Single and multiple stream configuration.

6.1.1.2 LOADCORE TEST PLANS

Control Plane: Number of registered subscribers in 5G core network

To measure the maximum number of registered state subscribers per AMF/SMF/AUSF/UDM. The rate of subscriber registration and release will also be recorded.

Control Plane: Number of connected subscribers

To measure the maximum number of connected state subscribers per AMF/SMF/UDM that triggered by the coming traffic. The rate of subscriber connection and release will also be recorded.

Control Plane: Number of PDU sessions per subscriber

To measure the maximum number of PDU session for one subscriber per AMF/SMF/AUSF/UDM.

User Plane: Number of buffered subscribers

To measure the maximum number of connected state subscribers per UPF.

User Plane: Number of user plane tunnels

To measure the maximum number of UP Tunnels per UPF

User Plane: 5G QoS flows

To measure the conformance of new 5G QoS Flow per UPF

User Plane: Number of serving subscribers per PLMN

To measure the maximum number of serving subscribers per UPF/SMF/NRF in the same PLMN.

User Plane: Number of VoNR voice call subscribers

To measure the maximum number of VoNR Voice Call subscribers per PCF/AF/NEF. The rate of subscriber VoNR Voice registration and deregistration will also be recorded.

User Plane: Number of VoNR video call subscribers

To measure the maximum number of VoNR Video Call subscribers per PCF/AF/NEF. The rate of subscriber VoNR Video registration and deregistration will also be recorded.

User Plane: Number of Serving subscribers per network slice

To measure the maximum number of serving subscribers per NSSF/AMF in the same slice

User Plane: 5G core network throughput measurement

To measure the maximum throughput of 5GC.

User Plane: 5G core network average delay

Measure the average delay in 5GC when forwarding traffic from the emulated RAN to the emulated Data Network.

User Plane: 5G core network packet loss

Measure the packet loss in 5GC when forwarding traffic from the emulated RAN to the emulated Data Network

User Plane: Dynamic user test

To measure the stability of the 5GC by emulating dynamic end users registration and deregistration.

6.1.2 MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGNS

This section describes the measurement campaigns that are created at the time of writing, based on the set of available test plans. They aggregate and bind different test plans into logical large tests. These campaigns can be executed regularly or on demand. The campaigns expose a number of parameters from the test plans contained within. These parameters are of two main types:.

- Metric parameters are relating to values of the generated traffic or actions by the test plan (e.g., bitrate, number of packets, file size, number of users, number of parallel streams, etc.).
- Context parameters are relating to what the test plan or tools used in the test plan should interact with (e.g., endpoint of UPF, port numbers, IP addresses, keys, certificates, IDs, frequencies, etc.).

Note that the campaigns listed here are created as simple aggregations of the test plans listed in previous section, meaning that more campaigns will be created as more test plans become available. The campaigns allows to run similar experimentations but changin a few high level parameters. As example, we could consider the same test campaign but with 3 traffic level (low, medium high) as an example. Test plans remains the same, but results will highly depend on the overall parameters.

Additionally, project partners and experimenters are free to create different campaigns aggregating exactly the set of test plans that are of most relevance to the specific experiment or component to be evaluated.

Application level campaign

- Adaptive Video: Video KPIs
- Network KPI: Packet Loss, Latency and Voice MOS
- Video Stream: Video MDI Scores
- Throughput: TCP/UDP Single/Multi stream Throughput

5G core user plane

- User Plane: Number of buffered subscribers
- User Plane: Number of user plane tunnels
- User Plane: 5G QoS flows
- User Plane: Number of serving subscribers per PLMN
- User Plane: Number of VoNR voice call subscribers
- User Plane: Number of VoNR video call subscribers
- User Plane: Number of Serving subscribers per network slice
- User Plane: 5G core network throughput measurement
- User Plane: 5G core network average delay
- User Plane: 5G core network packet loss
- User Plane: Dynamic user test

5G core control plane

- Control Plane: Number of registered subscribers in 5G core network
- Control Plane: Number of connected subscribers
- Control Plane: Number of PDU sessions per subscriber

6.1.2.1 PLAN FOR KPI EVALUATION (EXECUTIONS OF CAMPAIGNS)

For the network general test plans the intention is to execute the campaigns and evaluate KPIs periodically on the trial networks provided the trial network is continuously running and is available. For the trial networks being created on demand and for a specific experiment (short lived) it would be preferable that all campaigns are executed upon creation of the trial network. Alternatively, a subset of campaigns can be executed selected based on what the focus is of the current experiment, (e.g., if control plane of the 5G core is in focus because the experiment is concerning a SMF component, it might only be relevant to execute the “5G core control plane” campaign).

6.2 EVALUATION AND VALIDATION OF INTERNAL USE CASES

6.2.1 INTERNET OF SENSES

The use cases related with the Internet of Senses will be evaluated by defining a set of KPIs that should be measured in each run test. For each use case, several thresholds should be defined to consider if the result of the test is acceptable. This might be a pass/fail value or a level of acceptance of the set of KPIs.

KPIs will be measured depending on the involved sense. In the scope of this project, there are three types of senses: sight, hearing, and touch. Each one is stimulated by a particular content: sight is stimulated by video streams, hearing by audio streams and touch by sensations produced by a haptic device.

Audio and video streams are multimedia content and their KPIs are related:

- **Bitrate:** audio and video bitrate measured in kbps.
- **Loss rate:** or packet loss rate, is the rate between the number of video/audio packets that are transmitted but are not received in the end user device and the total number of transmitted packets.
- **Quality of Experience (QoE):** this KPI will be a subjective measurement provided by the end user of the test. It is related to the engagement of each person with the use case. It will relate to the multimedia content. It will be collected through a questionnaire that will be defined for each use case.
- **Power consumption:** of the test considering all the elements that can be measured of the communication pipeline. Measured in kWh.

KPIs related to haptic devices that will be collected are:

- **Quality of Experience (QoE):** similar to the KPI defined for the multimedia content but related to the experience with the haptic sensations.
- **Power consumption:** of the haptic devices. Measured in kWh.

Apart from the power consumption KPIs, all other KPIs are measured in the end user devices: VR headsets or standard video players for audio & video and the haptic devices themselves.

6.2.2 DIGITAL TWIN

For the Digital Twins (DT) two of its aspects need to be evaluated. The energy consumption where the Digital Twin predict the consumption based on the scenario given, and the Radio Performance where it predicts how the Radio is impacted by the channel and the network configuration given in the scenario.

They are producing the following KPIs:

- **Power Consumption:** the average power consumption for the given state of the network components in W.
- **BER:** the average Bit Error Rate the device has when confronted to specific channel condition (SINR) and network configuration (MCS, repetitions, ...) in percentage.
- **Throughput:** the actual average throughput achieved by the device when given a specific channel condition (SINR), network configuration (MCS, repetitions, ...), and incoming traffic in bit per seconds.

For the energy consumption validation, the ETSI standard measurement will be leveraged to ensure that the test is covering most of the typical use cases. It is composed of traffic scenarios [33]:

- **Low Load:** There is only a small amount of UEs exchanging small files over the networks
- **Medium Load:** The amount of UEs is increased slightly and the distribution favours bigger files compared to before.
- **Busy Hour Load:** The amount of UEs reflects a congested cells with many UEs, and files of varying sizes
- **Full Load:** The cell is used to its full capacity.

With these four scenarios, we can ensure that all possible traffic and network configurations are covered. These scenarios and their traffic data will be played in both the newly created DT and a testbed with the actual target of the DT. Then the DT will predict the energy consumption while the testbed will measure it. If the difference between the two are within 20% margins, we can use these results to confirm the validity of the approach.

For the Radio Performance the approach is similar, the DT and its equivalent testbed will receive a message with various degree of distortion under different network configurations (in this case, the main factor shall be SINR) and the difference between their produced values should be within 20%. In the case of the Radio Performance, this difference will be evaluated only in the reception part of the network components. The procedure will be to send the same message 100 times and see the average Bit Error Rate BER (%) and throughput (B/s) returned by the testbed and the DT.

6.3 KVI EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

6G-SANDBOX Deliverable D2.1 [1] provided an overview of KVIs and an assessment of general KVI categories. Certain KVIs have been identified for the KVI categories: (i) resilience, (ii) sustainability, and (iii) inclusiveness. To progress and refine the work with KVIs, and to steer ICT R&D activities to effectively address major societal needs, we sketch a conceptual framework as a series of steps from research at low Technology Readiness Level (TRL), up to deployment corresponding to high TRL. These steps should be understood as complementary to the steps identified in D2.1 in the context of their relevance for use cases and open calls.

Step I) Definition of scenario and use cases: In this step the global scenario that is addressed by the technological solution is outlined and instantiated to specific use cases.

Step II) Elicitation: Identification of key values (KVs) as criteria and key values as outcome to be associated with the use case.

Step IIIa) Analysis of outcome on value domains, leading to formulation of KVIs as metrics associated with the KVs for the use case. In this step, KVIs are formulated as absolute or relative measures of the impact of technology solution on the identified KVs. Use case KVIs will need to capture KVs that are both benefited as well as those that are detriment. This gives a possibility for formulating targets based on societal impact, and get a first-guess view of the expected outcome.

Step IIIb) Analysis of value proposition and estimation of use case proliferation, leading to an established view on the KVI outcome.

Step IIIc) Analysis involving prioritization and balance between KVIs and KPIs, leading to target formulations based in policy.

Step IV) Technical realization, involving identification and specification of enablers, potential formulation of KVIs associated to those, and a design iteration with respect to the KPIs and KVIs. In a more mature phase of development, the technology and system effects of providing a use case is better understood in terms of enablers.

Step V) Assessments, where KVIs can subsequently be gauged through a progression of evaluations, notably Va) expert assessments, Vb) simulations, and Vc) twinned systems. Assessment should be done with defined methodologies and can lead to a reformulation of KVIs and associated targets based on an increased understanding. Mitigating actions, related to the technical enablers and service solution of the use case, can also be launched as an outcome of these assessments to avoid negative impacts and regain positive impacts. In a final step Vd), after deployment of the use case, the outcome on KVIs can be gauged with defined methodologies adapted to the specific use case (to be developed), and subsequently compared with formulated targets, after which the value impact can be concluded.

For this document we will focus on assessment or KVI evaluation aspects in Step V. by providing guidance for assessing how the use of 6G network and use case solutions impact KVIs formulated for the specific use cases / socio-technical systems. The outcome of the assessment of a KVI can reflect the enhancement of a key value due to the introduction of the 6G solution, or avoidance/mitigation action on a negative trend on a key value due to external factors and addresses both positive and negative effects on the measure.

Besides gauging the level of the KVIs, the drivers, i.e. the metrics that have the most impact – both negative and positive – on the KVI need to be identified. In the subsequent step it is determined whether the KVI can be expressed as a formula of the drivers: ideally, we should be able to express the KVI as a function of all or some of the drivers - but this may not always be achievable.

In the following, we consider the assessment of the use of an 6G-based solution in a (present or potential) usage scenario. The metrics related to the impact of an 6G-based solution are derived based on a case study, i.e., the effect of the solution is calculated for a specific setting and the results can be used to model its effects in a different situation. When considering the impact of 6G solutions on KVs, we consider effects of multiple orders. First order effects are the ones that come from the direct deployment of the technology (from the deployment and operation of the 6G solution itself), e.g., creation of jobs or facilities or infrastructure energy requirements. Second order effects reflect the enabling of new services, the modification of old ones or substitution – where the new service substitute an existing one. This can mean optimization of processes leading to a change in KVIs or the introduction of new functionalities and usage possibilities impacting the KVIs. Higher order effects describe rebound effects, reflected in behaviour changes of the broader society. Enablement of new usages would e.g. trigger a behaviour change; optimizations would lead to more efficient operations. Rebound effects describe situations in which enhanced efficiency of processes/resource usage does not lead to an overall decrease in resource usage, but instead to a higher consumption of resources in absolute terms. This occurs if a service is delivered more efficiently, but in consequence is used to a substantially higher degree thus leading to a rise in required resources overall. Considering more general values, such as decarbonization goals, it can also refer to efficiency gains in one sector, e.g. less kilometres travelled to work due to home office possibilities, which lead to more resource consumption using saved resources (time, money) for a different activity, e.g. more kilometres travelled for leisure purposes. While rebound effects are difficult to estimate, they are very important to consider getting an idea of the actual overall impact of 6G solutions on key values¹:

- Relevance: Selected data and methods shall be appropriate to the assessment.
- Completeness: All outcome that influence the KVI and contribute to the overall result shall be included and assessed.
- Consistency: Meaningful analysis regarding the development of results over time shall be enabled by using the same methodological approaches for compared results.
- Accuracy: Biases and uncertainties shall be reduced as far as practicable.
- Transparency: When communicating the results, sufficient information shall be given to support the interpretation of the results. This means that data sources, data collection processes as well as the modelling and the assumptions made shall be clearly stated and motivated in the documentation, as well as all the assessment boundaries and cut-offs.
- Conservativeness: Conservative assumptions and values shall be used when there are uncertainties. Conservative quantification results are underestimated rather than overestimated.

The KVIs assessment can go through various steps of progressing complexity and realism, for each of which specific methodologies should be defined, as outlined in the following.

6.3.1 VA) EXPERT ASSESSMENTS

Expert Assessment, in response to the question of evaluating a KVI (or a collection of KVIs), provides an interpretation, opinion or recommendation, as much as possible based on objective criteria, and devised from available data, knowledge and observations. The assessment requires independence, neutrality, and impartiality. Requirements on referred data quality should be defined.

¹ ITU-T Recommendation L.1480, <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-L.1480-202212-I>.

To properly assess the KVI, it is necessary to define the specific context (use case or scenario); the implementation scale (organization, city, region, worldwide); which group of stakeholders is it affecting (e.g., all users/citizens, some users/citizens, specific targeted users/citizens).

Assessments can happen from three different time perspectives:

- Ex-ante, i.e., the assessment is taking place before the deployment and operation of the use case;
- Mid-way, i.e., the assessment is taking during the operational life of the use case and reflects a present situation.
- Ex-post, i.e., assessment is taking place retrospectively, and takes place after the assessed operation period of the use case.

Also, the type of the assessment should be defined. It must be specified whether the assessment is referring to the specific implementation of one or several use cases, or to a general usage.

6.3.2 VB) SIMULATIONS

Socio-technical systems represent a conceptual framework enabling the simulation of how these systems respond to the integration of new ICT solutions. This process involves modelling the socio-technical system, conducting simulations, and gathering data to quantify the impact of each evaluated ICT.

6.3.3 VC) TWINNED SYSTEMS

Digital twins, as simulation, rely on model-based simulations, but they are not the same. The digital twin of a system allows, through (near) real time collection of data (e.g. gathering input from connected sensors, machinery, and people) to see how it is operating in (near) real time. Unlike simulation, it is Ex-ante and Mid-way assessments, since it is not limited to looking back at a scenario, but also can be used for in advance what-if analysis before introducing an ICT solution.

A digital twin integrates simulations of the use case it represents, which can operate at different levels of specificity (e.g. device, process, or even plant level) and combines real-time data and system-level behaviour modelling.

6.3.4 VD) ACTUAL SYSTEM

Once the use case is deployed, either with general availability or in a more limited test scenario, the outcome on KVI can be directly measured. Specific methodologies are defined, and subsequently compared with formulated targets or baseline scenarios, after which the value impact can be concluded.,

The steps from Va) to Vc) assessments can lead to a reformulation of KVI and associated targets based on an increased understanding. Mitigating actions on the development can also be launched as an outcome of these assessments to avoid negative impacts and regain positive impacts.

The evaluation methods for a selection of KVI drawn upon example use cases are provided in Table 1 below. Each of these KVI can be evaluated through methods that must be identified in each of the aforementioned steps. Hereby we define evaluation as the process of computing quantitative information of some characteristics of a certain solution. However, not for all characteristics quantitative information can be computed, therefore, qualitative evaluation should be allowed. Furthermore, not all evaluation steps (expert assessment, simulation, twinned system, actual system) are suitable for all identified KVI and a choice must be made as to which steps and methods are most suitable. Table 1 below provides an initial assessment about the suitability of evaluation methods to evaluate the example KVI.

Table 1 Evaluation methods for a selection of KVIs.

KVI	Evaluation step
Number of incidents of health problems caused by air pollution in the city - measured in % decrease compared to current baseline	<p><i>Simulation</i> based on suitable models can provide a theoretical estimate of the expected reduction in health incidents.</p> <p>In complement, the <i>actual system</i> can provide data that can be compared to agreed baselines, <i>expert assessment</i> can provide professional judgment on the potential impact of the proposed solution, and a <i>twinned system</i> can be used to relate real-time data for judging the effectiveness of the solution.,</p>
Severity of incidents of health problems caused by air pollution in the city - measured in % decrease compared to current baseline	<p>Due to the nature of the indicator, <i>expert assessment</i> is the best evaluation method that can consider factors like complexity of severity measurement, severity and context sensitivity as well as multi-dimensional factors like hospitalization rates, disease progression and long-term effects.</p> <p>While <i>simulation</i>, <i>twinned system</i>, and <i>actual system</i> evaluations are valuable for assessing various aspects, they may not capture the full complexity of severity assessments as effectively as expert judgment.</p>
Efficiency in the detection of dangerous areas for vulnerable groups - measured in % increase compared to current baseline	<p>A <i>twinned system</i> through real-time data integration, proactive monitoring and scenario-based <i>simulation</i> appears to be the best way to evaluate this KVI, because it could be constructed with a feedback loop for incorporating improvements.</p> <p><i>Expert assessment</i> and <i>actual system</i> may not be able to respond properly to the dynamic nature of the KVI and the need for fast adaptation.</p>
Life expectancy for city population - measured in % increase compared to current baseline	<p>Being a long-term metric this KVI should be evaluated through <i>actual system</i> measurements, since the evaluation depends on reliability of data, historical data and trends and is strongly influenced by secondary parameters like lifestyle choices and public health programs.</p> <p>While <i>expert assessment</i>, <i>simulation</i>, and <i>twinned system</i> evaluations could be used in certain contexts, life expectancy is a fundamental health indicator that is best assessed through the collection and analysis of real-world data.</p>

7 CONCLUSION

The document outlines the endeavours related to the methodology for conducting tests and experiments. It focuses on the approach for defining and implementing those tests and experiments, how to realize them, how to practically evaluate KPIs and KQIs, and how to automate the related process. The goal of the document is to provide definition of the methodology for defining KPI and KQI and describe the system used for realizing their evaluation. This also includes description of the such a system and how it interacts with the 6G-SANDBOX trial networks.

Moreover, the document provides a summary of the formal definitions of test cases, scenario and slices which is the foundation for defining tests and experiments. The document proceeds to detail the test automation cloud platform which provides functionalities to realize the formal methodology in a practical and automated manner. It is also described how the test automation platform integrates with tools and trial networks. Next an overview is given of all the test and measurement equipment and tools made available in the project, along with descriptions of what they do. Then the approach for test reporting and result collection is presented and it is described how KPIs, KQIs and use cases are evaluated practically.

The document does not provide a complete and fixed description of all test cases and scenarios together with a fixed list of test plans and campaigns. This is simply not feasible as the landscape continuously changes in terms of trial network, the 6G components going into the trial network, the use cases and experiments being evaluated on the trial networks, the tools and equipment available to support test and measurements. For that reason, this document provides a starting point and methodology for how evaluate KPIs, KQIs and use cases, but will let it be up to experimenters to create the specific content needed for evaluation.

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ANNEX 1 CARTOGRAPHY OF THE CAPABILITIES PER PLATFORM

The table below is originally presented in “Experimenter Facility Capability Overview” [32].

6GSANDBOX Cartography (date for availability to be confirmed with platforms)							
Category	Component	HW/SW	Description	Example	Berlin	Athens	Malaga
RAN	5G RAN	HW	5G Radio + Baseband, Bands n77, n78, FR2	Nokia Airscale	X		
	5G RAN	HW	5G Radio + Baseband, Bands n78	Nokia Airscale , Huawei	X		
	5G RAN	HW	5G Radio + Baseband, Bands n78, n7, n28	Amarisoft Classic		X	
	5G RAN	HW	5G Radio + Baseband, Bands n78, FR2	Ericsson		X	
	5G RAN	HW	5G Radio + Baseband, Band n78, FR2	Nokia Airscale			X
	5G RAN	HW	Software Defined Radio	National Instruments B210	X		
	5G RAN	HW	Software Defined Radio	National Instruments N310			X
	OpenRAN	HW	RU, Band n77u, Band 78	Benetel RAN650, Benetel RAN550	X		X
	OpenRAN	SW	DU + CU	IS-Wireless			X
	RIS	HW		Queen University of Belfast-RIS			X
	5G gNodeB Simulator	SW	gNodeB + UE Simulator	UERANSIM	X	X	X
	Simulator	HW/SW	UE emulator RAN solutions	UeSim			X
	Simulator	HW/SW	O-CU Midhaul solutions	DuSim			X
	Simulator	HW/SW	O-DU Midhaul solutions	CuSim			X
	Simulator	HW/SW	UE/O-RU emulation over the O-RAN fronthaul	RuSim			X
	Analyzer	HW	Power analyzer	Keysight N6705c DC Power analyzer			X
	Analyzer	HW	Power analyzer	AC6803 AC Power Source	X		
	Functional tester	HW/SW	O-RAN testing	Keysight O-RAN Studio for o-RU testing			X
	Signal generator	HW	5G Wireless test platform	Keysight UXM 5G E7515B			X
	Signal generator	HW	Microwave signal generator	Keysight VXG			X
Analyzer	HW	Power analyzer	Keysight AC Power Analyzer			X	
Signal generator	HW	RF test platform	Keysight MTRX			X	
Traffic Generator	HW/SW	Drive test and analytics	Keysight Nemo Wireless solutions			X	

	Simulator	SW	Link level simulator	Keysight System Vue			X
	Performance testing	SW	Link level simulator	Keysight RIC Tester			X
	Analyzer	HW	Link level simulator	Keysight Sanjole wireless analyzer			X
5G Core	5G Core	SW	Full 5G Core	Open5GS	X	X	X
	5G Core	HW/SW	Full 5G Core	Amarisoft Classic	X	X	
	5G Core	SW	Full 5G Core	free5GC		X	
	5G Core	SW	LMF	LMF		X	
	5G Core	SW	NWDAF	NWDAF		X	X
	5G Core	SW	NEF	NEF Emulator		X	
	5G Core	SW	Full 5G Core	Open5GCore	X		
	5G Core	SW	Full 5G Core	ATHONET 5GC		X	
	5G Core	SW	Full 5G Core	Polaris 5GC			X
	Slices	SW	5G Slices preconfigured in the Testbed	Slice A, Slice B			X
	UPF	HW/SW	Stand Alone UPF	UPF from Open5GS, P4-UPF		X	X
	UPF	HW/SW	Stand Alone UPF	ATHONET UPF		X	
	Functional tester and traffic generator	SW	5G core testing and emulation	Keysight LoadCore	X	X	X
6GLibrary	Repository	SW	6GSANDBOX Library repo (mostly in the Cloud)	GitHub	X	X	X
	Artifacts	SW	Objects in 6GLibrary (mostly in the Cloud)	AWS ECR, Open Nebula Marketplace	X	X	X
Compute	Cloud Manager	SW	Server manager to create VMs, Containers, etc	Open Nebula, XXX	X	X	X
Compute	Virtual Machine	SW	KVM Virtual Machine	KVM Virtualization	X		X
	Virtual Machine	SW	VMware Virtual Machine		X		
	Virtual networks	SW	Virtual Networks, VLAN, VXLAN, ...	Open Nebula, XXX	X	X	X
	Kubernetes Cluster	SW	Kubernetes Cluster solution compatible with vanilla K8s	ONEKE			X
	GPUs	HW	GPU Cards with PCI bus	Nvidia RX2070 Super			
	GPUs	HW	GPU Cards with PCI bus	Nvidia A10		X	
	GPUs	HW	GPU Cards with PCI bus	Nvidia RTX4080, Nvidia T4			X
	Accelerators	HW	Accelerators cards with PCI Bus	FPGAs, SmartNICs, ...			
	Performance testing	SW	NFVI performance testing	Keysight CloudPeak		X	X

	Performance testing	SW	Cloud scalability and security	Keysight Cyperf	X	X	
Network	Fiber Switch	HW	Datacenter Switches to connect RAN, Servers, etc	Mellanox XXXX	X		
	Fiber Switch	HW	Datacenter Switches to connect RAN, Servers, etc	Mikrotic, CISCO Nexus, HP Aruba/Flexfabric	X	X	
	Switch	HW	Datacenter switches to connect, RAN, Servers, etc	Netgear, P4 switches			X
	Time Sensitive Networking	HW	TSN endpoints and bridge				X
	Firewall	SW	Firewall/Bastion to provide access to Trial Network through VPN	PFSense	X	X	
	NTP	SW	NTP service for Time synchronization	OpenNTPD			X
	MTIP	SW	Multiconectity transport protocol	UMA implementation			X
	DNS	SW	DNS service for Trial Networks	BIND			X
	Satellite Backhaul	HW/SW	Satellite Backhaul for the testbed	Starlink	X	X	X
	Satellite Emulator	SW	end-to-end satellite communication system	OpenSAND	X		
	SDN	SW	SDN Controller to manage connectivity	TBD	X		
	Digital twin	SW	Network digital twin platform	Keysight EXata	X	X	X
	Traffic Generator	SW	Application layer traffic emulator	Keysight Hawkeye	X	X	X
Network	Security testing	SW	Security pen-testting	Keysight BreakingPoint	X	X	
	Traffic Generator	SW	L2-L3 network performance	Keysight IxNetwork	X	X	
	Traffic Generator	SW	L4-L7 traffic generator	Keysight IxLoad	X	X	
	Security testing	SW	Security testing and vulnerability scanning	Keysight Threat Simulator	X	X	
	Simulator	HW	Impairment emulator	Keysight Network Emulator 3			X
Storage	Shared Storage	HW/SW	Shared storage for the datacenter	CEPH	X		
Operation	CPD Monitoring	SW	Monitoring system collecting metrics for infrastructure	Prometheus	X	X	X
	TN KPIs	SW	Monitoring system collecting metrics for Trial Networks	InfluxDB	X	X	X

	Dashboards	SW	Operational Dashboards for Datacenter infrastructure	Grafana	X	X	X
	Alerts	SW	Alerting system for Datacenter infrastructure	Prometheus, Grafana			X
Automation	TNLCM	SW	Trial Network Lifecycle Manager	TNLCM	X	X	X
	Orchestrator	SW	Orchestrator used by. Automation	Jenkins	X		X
	IaC Manager	SW	Infrastructure as Code manager to create VMs, K8s clusters, etc	Terraform	X	X	X
	Configuration Mgr	SW	Tool to apply configurations to deployed components	Ansible	X	X	X
	Deployment Mgr	SW	Tool to deploy Containerized components from 6GLibrary	Helm	X	X	X
Automation	Test automation	SW	Test automation and sequencing	OpenTAP/PathWave Test Automation Cloud	X	X	X

ANNEX 2 6G-SANDBOX GLOSSARY

Term	Description
6G KPI and KVI repository	To maximize the contribution towards a 6G experimentation ecosystem, all the results of the experimentation processes performed on the 6G-SANDBOX facility will be stored in an open 6G KPI & KVI repository following a common and structured format (based on the SNS JU work in the related WGs) and they will be accessible by other projects/stakeholders, and thus, subject to external analysis.
6G Library	To support reusability, openness, and long-term evolution a meaningful set of software components -that will be provided to and/or developed for the 6G-SANDBOX facility - will be packed and offered in a relevant repository (e.g., GitHub) together with the required documentation in order to create an open reference software library, which will not only be under continuous enhancement by the project partners, but it is also meant to serve as an index and sink point for other developments (during and beyond the project lifetime).
Architecture (or Reference Architecture)	The main representation of the 6G-SANDBOX facility . It can be provided in various levels of detail (abstractions) or viewpoints (e.g., functional, topology, implementation etc.). A first version of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture is in the proposal/DoA. Based on the components, the interfaces, the technologies, the tools, and the structure that might be depicted in the Reference Architecture, the development teams should be able to implement the relevant functions, processes, and services.
Experimentation lifecycle Layer	The upper layer of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture . It includes the functions and the components needed for controlling the experimentation process and providing the required access to the experimenters.
Experimentation platform (or Platform)	An End-to-End platform (a system with integrated Radio Access Network, Network Core, Transport and services) that include 6G-enabled components/features and experimentation services as well as local cloud infrastructure capabilities. Four platforms support the 6G-SANDBOX project, namely the Malaga platform, the Athens Platform, the Berlin platform, and the Oulu platform.
Facility (or the 6G-SANDBOX facility) (or 6G-Experimentation facility)	The full set of 6G-SANDBOX components that are offered as a pan-European testbed for testing. The testing procedures can be for 6G technology validations and for 6G KPI measurements. The facility is expected to include the implementation of all the components that will be structured around a 6G-SANDBOX reference architecture.
Node	It refers to every physical or virtual component that can be identified individually, i.e., it has specific purpose (provides a kind of service) and it encompass one or multiple technological features. Examples are a 5G-NR antenna, a RIS system, an IoT end-device, a network application, a network function, a set of network functions that compose network core, an experimentation tool, etc.
KPI measurement campaigns (or 6G KPI measurements)	Tests using the 6G-SANDBOX testbed targeting the quantification (selection of values) for well-defined KPIs (e.g., KPIs defined in the 6G-SANDBOX proposal/DoA, or selected ones from the related SNS JU work group).
Physical Infrastructure Layer	The lower layer of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture . It includes the functions and the components needed for providing end-to-end 6G-enabled connectivity (each of the 4 6G-SANDBOX platforms are included here)

Resource Management Layer	<p>The mid layer of the 6G-SANDBOX Reference Architecture. It manages computational and network resources and forming them as Trial Networks to be offered for experimentation. It may operate in a cross-platform manner / above the local (platform specific) controllers and managers. It may also include functions and components needed for optimizing the Trial Networks, e.g., with AI capabilities and Security guarantees.</p>
Site (or Platform's Site) (or Experimentation platform's Site)	<p>A location-dependent part of an experimentation platform. The various sites of a platform should be well interconnected and interfaced, but this interconnection and interfacing is not necessarily exposed to platform externals. Example: the Athens platform of 6G-SANDBOX is composed of parts that are located in the COSMOTE premises (i.e., parts that define the COSMOTE site of the platform, e.g., the 5G core) and parts at the NCSR campus (i.e., parts that define the NCSR site of the platform, e.g., the 5G access); these two sites are well-connected with an optical fiber link.</p>
Technology validation test (or 6G Technology validation)	<p>Tests using the 6G-SANDBOX facility targeting to assess whether a component/node operates and interacts properly, and also provide expected results. The Technology validation tests target the assessment of components/nodes within an overall system. E.g., the tests to validate that the API framework of 6G-SANDBOX is well integrated in the overall testbed.</p>
Third Party	<p>The Third Party is an organization (commercial or not-for-profit) that participates in and or uses the 6G-SANDBOX facility without being part of the 6G-SANDBOX consortium. The Third Party can be identified via an Open Call procedure or via an in-kind contribution or a direct engagement.</p>
Trial Networks	<p>Fully configurable, manageable and controllable network which combines digital/virtual and physical nodes and provides services for 6G technology validation and 6G KPI measurements. Instances of Trial Networks might be offered targeting specific network domains and technologies. End-to-end Trial Networks will be offered by the four experimentation platforms that support the 6G-SANDBOX project.</p>